

Action of *N*-bromosuccinimide-dimethyl sulphoxide on camphor and its oxime derivative

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Abstract : Reaction of *N*-bromosuccinimide-dimethyl sulphoxide (NBS/DMSO) has been carried out on cyclic monoterpenoid taking camphor and its 2-keto oxime derivative as the starting material. The compounds obtained as a result of the reaction have been characterized and identified by spectroscopic analysis (IR, NMR) and by mass spectral data.

Keywords : Camphor, NBS, DMSO.

Introduction

N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) has been in use for allylic bromination since 1919, when Wohl and then Zeigler made detailed studies on application of the reagent for allylic bromination. The reagent also reacts with olefins to add bromine to the double bond or acts as a source of hypohalous acid in aqueous solution. The reagent is also in extensive use since 1969 as an effective reagent for the oxidation of allylic methylene to carbonyl functionality. Many reviews have appeared on the action of NBS; of them (a) Djerassi and (b) Homer and Wenkelman for allylic bromination and (c) Filler on bromination and oxidation reactions are worth mentioning. Application of it on terpenoids, mostly on triterpenoids¹⁻¹³ and some of them on diterpenoids¹⁴⁻¹⁷ have been reported by several groups of workers.

However, limited reports on the investigation of NBS in DMSO solvent on monoterpenoids¹⁸⁻²¹ have encouraged the author to study the influence of this useful oxidizing agent on some monoterpenoids taking camphor as a model compound. In addition the author has further extended the reaction on oxime derivative of camphor.

Results and discussion

Reaction of camphor (**1**) on treatment with molar equivalent of NBS-DMSO in CHCl₃ (Scheme 1) in the usual manner²² afforded a gummy residue, which was purified by column chromatography [petroleum ether-ethyl

acetate mixture (4 : 1)] followed by repeated crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture to afford compound **2**, m.p. 155–160 °C. It gave an intense green flame in Beilstein test showing the presence of bromine in **2**. From elemental analysis and mass spectral data, molecular formula of the compound was found to be C₁₀H₁₄OBr₂, which was supported by the existence of three molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 308, 310 and 312 in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 (for the presence of two bromine atoms) in compound **2**. Its IR spectrum showed a peak at 1743 cm⁻¹ for the carbonyl stretching vibration. Its ¹H NMR spectrum showed a broad multiplet centred at δ 0.91 for six protons for two geminal methyls, a multiplet at 1.93 ppm for three protons showed the presence of another methyl group, two methylene protons each at C-5 and C-6 appeared as a multiplet centred at 1.68 and 1.37 ppm respectively and the methine proton at C-4 also appeared as a multiplet centred at 2.34 ppm. Its ¹³C NMR spectrum showed the presence of all the ten carbons. The newly developed quaternary carbon alpha to the carbonyl group appeared at 57.6. Peak for carbonyl carbon appeared at 210.0 ppm with very low intensity which may be due to the low relaxation time as well as for the quadruple effect. Thus from the above result the structure for compound **2** was confirmed.

Similar reaction on the oxime derivative **3** of camphor, prepared by the treatment of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of small amount of pyridine on cam-

phor, with molar equivalent of NBS-DMSO in CHCl_3 in the usual manner (Scheme 1) afforded a single compound **4** after column chromatographic separation. The compound was purified by repeated crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture to get white crystal of **4**, m.p.

Scheme 1

103–105 °C, gave an intense green flame in Beilstein test for the presence of bromine in **4**. Elemental analysis indicated the molecular formula of $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{ONBr}_2$ for **4** which was supported by the existence of three ion peaks at m/z 323, 325 and 327 for $[\text{M}^+]$ in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 providing the presence of two bromine atoms. The other important peaks appeared at m/z 309, 311 and 313 $[\text{M}-\text{N}]^+$; 281 $[\text{M}-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2]^+$; 267, 265, 251, 221, 207, 178, 163 and 147 (100%). Its IR spectrum showed a broad peak at 3300–3400 cm^{-1} and other peaks at 1170, 948.9 and 725.2 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectrum showed the presence of three methyl peaks each integrated for three protons at δ 0.95, 0.78 and 0.84. A broad signal centred at 8.00 appeared for the proton of $=\text{N}-\text{OH}$. Its ^{13}C NMR spectrum showed all the ten carbons. Peak at δ 168.0 was due to the carbon of $\text{C}=\text{NOH}$ group and the newly developed quaternary carbon at C-3 appeared at 50.83. Thus from the above analysis the structure of compound **4** was confirmed.

Reaction mechanism :

In a highly polar solvent like DMSO, **1** enolizes to give the enol form **1a** which undergoes allylic bromination at C-3 to give the thermodynamically controlled compound **1b**. The dibromide **2** would be formed by bromi-

nation of the bromo ketone **1b** either by radical mechanism or by further allylic bromination on **1c** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used during the investigation had the b.p. 60–80 °C. IR spectra were taken in KBr on Shimadzu FT-IR 8300 spectrophotometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometers using CDCl_3 solution containing TMS as reference. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL-AccuToF JMS-T100LC spectrometer. All the rotations were taken in CHCl_3 solution. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine vapour.

General procedure for bromination²² :

A solution of camphor/oxime derivative of camphor (1/3) (3 g) in chloroform (150 mL) was mixed with dimethyl sulphoxide (75 mL). *N*-Bromosuccinimide (3.5 g) was then added to it in small lots in order to keep the temperature of the reaction mixture below 25 °C and the mixture kept in dark for 10 days. It was extracted with chloroform and washed several times with water, dried anhydrous (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue (2.8 g) was chromatographed over silica gel column, developed with petroleum ether and purified by repeated crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture yielded white crystalline solid.

Compound 2 :

White crystalline solid, yield 94%; Found : C, 38.60; H, 4.50. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{14}OBr_2$ (308) : C, 38.30; H, 4.70%; m.p. 155–160 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1743 (CO), 1180; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 0.91 (6H, broad m, for two geminal methyls at C-7), 1.93 (3H, m, for $-CH_3$ at C-1), 1.37 (2H, m, for C-6), 1.68 (2H, m, for C_5 -2H), 2.34 (1H, m, at C-4); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 9.2 (C-10), 19.1, 19.7 (C-8 and C-9), 46.7 (C-7), 29.9 (C-6), 27.0 (C-5), 43.2 (C-4), 43.0 (C-3), 210.0 (CO, C-2), 57.6 (C-1); MS : m/z 308 $[M]^+$, 310 $[M+2]^+$ and 312 $[M+4]^+$ (1 : 2 : 1), 293 $[M-CH_3]^+$, 295 $[(M+2)-CH_3]^+$, 297 $[(M+4)-CH_3]^+$ (1 : 2 : 1), 154 $[(M+4)-Br_2]^+$ (100%).

Preparation of oxime derivative of camphor :

To a solution of camphor (3.0 g) dissolved in pyridine (30 mL) was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.0 g) and ethanol (150 mL). The mixture was then refluxed on water bath for 4 h. It was then cooled and poured over ice-cold water when white solid separated out. It was washed with water filtered through suction and dried. The dried mass was crystallized several times with chloroform-methanol mixture when camphor oxime **3**, m.p. 118–119 °C (lit.²³ m.p. 115–119 °C) was obtained. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3450–3200, 1640.

Compound 4 :

White crystalline solid, yield 95%; Found : C, 35.65; H, 4.81. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{15}ONBr_2$ (323) : C, 35.71; H, 4.73%; m.p. 103–105 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3300–3400, 1170, 948.9 and 725.2; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 0.95 (for C-10), 0.78, 0.84 (for C-8 and C-9). The remaining protons have resonance signals between δ 1.00 and 3.00 from TMS. A broad signal for the proton of $=N-OH$ group in between δ 7.00 to 9.00 from TMS; ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 10.0 (C-10), 17.5, 18.4 (C-8, C-9), 26.2 (C-5), 31.5 (C-6), 47.2 (C-3), 50.8 (C-4), 32.1 (C-7), 42.6 (C-1) and peak for (C-2) quaternary carbon appeared at 168. MS : m/z 323 $[M]^+$, 325 $[M+2]^+$ and 327 $[M+4]^+$ in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 (two bromine atoms) 309, 311, 313 $[M-N]^+$; 281 $[M-$

$C(CH_3)_2]^+$; 267, 265, 251, 221, 207, 178, 163 and 147 (100%).

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